

BURMA
CHILD SOLDIERING WORLD CHAMPION

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Author's biography

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At the moment he lives in Thailand where he is carrying out his fieldwork on the situation of Burmese child soldiers, focusing on the problem of Burma National Army deserters living in Thailand.

He has been working in the area for four years. During this time, he has participated in a number of internships in local NGO's as well as international organizations in projects like: *A Culture of Peace in Cambodia*, sponsored by UNESCO Japan; *Peace Building in East Timor*, sponsored by MOFA Japan; *The Burma Project*, at Forum Asia for Human Rights and Development; and *Violence Prevention Against Children in Southeast Asia* at the Child Protection Office of UNICEF's Southeast Asia and the Pacific Regional Office.

Abstract

The article explores one of the most widespread human rights violations in Burma: the military recruitment of children to armed groups.

Based on previous research and interviews carried out with humanitarian organizations at the Thai-Burmese boarder the article shows how in spite of a comprehensive legal framework -both international and national- that explicitly prohibits it, recruitment of underage boys continues -mainly, though not exclusively, at the country's National Army: the Tatmadaw-; and how demobilization and reintegration of child soldiers continues to remain *desirable* and *uncertain*.

1. CHILD SOLDIERING WORLD CHAMPION

“With the Burmese Army it was like hell...” (CSW Report. 2003)ⁱ

*“To be a boy in Burma today means facing the constant risk of being picked up off the street, forced to commit atrocities, and never seeing your family again”*ⁱⁱⁱ (Becker. 2002)

Child recruitment in Burma is widespread, 20~45% of its active soldiers are under 18. According to Human Rights Watch (HRW. 2004)ⁱⁱⁱ and UNICEF (2002)^{iv} the estimated 70,000 children in the National Army alone make up one quarter of the child soldiers in the world. Voluntary and coerced recruitment happens in the National and opposition armies and includes children as young as nine. Yet, a taboo blanket covers it all; the issue is politically charged to such an extent that researching about it, making estimations, offering humanitarian assistance or implementing any DDRR¹ program for those children seems impossible.

Children serving in opposition groups are thought to be decreasing due to shrinking and splitting of the groups. Still, the army holding the gross number of child soldiers is the Tatmadaw -Burma National Army-. Thus, a decline in the number of child soldiers in minority groups does not necessarily mean a reduction in the number of child soldiers at the national level. Still SPDC² insists that it is unreasonably accused: *“saboteurs at home and abroad, are trying to discredit the government, are alleging the government recruits juvenile soldiers for the front lines...”* (Irrawady. 2005)^v

In Burma child soldiering encloses significant differences in terms of nature, causes and consequences among opposition groups and Tatmadaw. All parties claim to have *only volunteer soldiers who are above 18*, but the extent of that *volunteering* differs greatly from group. Key differences relate to amount of children, recruitment method and motivation. Tatmadaw is thought to have 70,000 child soldiers while opposition groups combined have 6~7,000.

Research suggests that most Tatmadaw children would escape if they could, while children in rebel groups do not normally want to be demobilized.

Entry into Tatmadaw is based on coercion: from officials; from children’s families and communities; or aloneness. In rebel groups the personal motivation to join is usually related to a sense of self-defense. Opposition groups recruit children on volunteer and forced bases, although this is more difficult probe due to: recruitment and demobilization methods; the smaller numbers of children; the amount of groups; geographical and security accessibility; and the difference in terms of volunteering.

Of over 30 opposition groups, 17 have agreed ceasefires with SPDC, yet HRW documented the use of child soldiers by 19 of them in 2002.

Children join rebel armies after they see their families slaughtered by SPDC soldiers, they join opposition armies for they want revenge, they join to find a place to belong to, and to have something to do. Unlike children enlisted by SPDC, these kids are not forced to walk across unmapped minefields; they usually can go home whenever they want, except for the fact that many of them do not have a home to return to.

Some groups show sensitivity towards letting children out the conflict and interest in providing alternatives for those who want to join, while others deny their existence despite evidence to the contrary. According to UNICEF *“most of them still do not see it as a moral or ethical commitment to their own children.”*^{vi}

¹ DDRR Demobilization, Disarmament, Rehabilitation and Reintegration

² SPDC: Security, Peace and Development Council, military Junta ruling the country since 1988

Top rank commanders in some ethnic armies admit that 20% of the group's soldiers are under 18. While they seem to be aware of international standards and sustain that *"We would exclude children from our forces, but most of the children who seek to join are displaced or refugee seekers who do it because they lack opportunities (...)"*^{vii}

2. DOES THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK HELP US?

Two main instruments provide the legal framework to approach our case: The UN Convention on the Rights of the Child (CRC) and the 1993 Burmese Child Law.

While the CRC prohibits the recruitment of children under 15, the Burmese law sets the limit at 18. This law defines penalties in its section 65, where it reads *"employing or permitting a child to perform work which is hazardous to the life of the child or which may cause disease to the child or which is harmful to the child's moral character is punishable by imprisonment of up to six months or a fine, or both."*

According to SPDC the Child Law materializes the rights of the child recognized by the CRC; in so doing its Chapter V, section 8 reads *"...the State recognizes that every child has the right to survival, development, protection and care, and to achieve active participation in the community."*

Burma ratified the CRC in 1991 and soon after sanctioned its Child Law to provide better legal protection to children; however implementation falls behind; the Junta has systematically refused to sign the Optional Protocol to the CRC on the Involvement of Children in Armed Conflict, which prohibits the recruitment of under 18's and it continues to deny access to external monitoring organisms.

In spite of legal restrictions, evidence shows that child rights violations continue; child recruitment persists and DDRR cannot be verified, all of which suggests that even if laws to protect children are in place, little is done to enforce them.

3. WHAT MAKES BURMA'S CHILD SOLDIERS UNIQUE

A number of related aspects provide understanding on why child soldiering is such a distinctive feature of the conflict in Burma:

- 1) The general chaos of the human rights;
- 2) Burma's armed conflict is the longest in the history of independent states;
- 3) General acceptance of the *Child Soldier Doctrine*^{viii} by most parties to the conflict;
- 4) Child conscription happens on volunteer and coerced bases -whatever the cause-;
- 5) Coercion of children to do hard labor, particularly related to porters, shows that kids do not need uniforms or guns to be soldiers;
- 6) Food for the Tatmadaw in border areas is an essential aspect to understand the use of children in the national army. Tatmadaw needs to bring food to the areas where it fights opposition groups and food is heavy to carry;
- 7) The size of Tatmadaw deserves consideration; since keeping this huge army with limited economical resources requires a strategy that allows it to hold its soldiers. This strategy is not based on a professional force, with motivated warriors; but it relies on forced recruitment and a mechanism of fear. Children are easy to recruit, cheap, accountable and do not question.

- 8) Mass desertions happen in Tatmadaw. This worsens the army shortage of soldiers and increases pressures on recruiters to raise their quota of new soldiers, which “*inevitably means many young men are still being targeted*” Jagan (2007)^{ix}.
- 9) Child recruitment normally takes place in rural areas rather than in big cities.
- 11) Other factors that lead to the enlistment of children include poverty, displacement, lack of opportunities and jobs, children *volunteer* out of desperation.

4. UNOFFICIAL RECRUITMENT OF CHILDREN

In Tatmadaw there are three categories of child soldiers: the biggest group formed by children forcedly conscripted. The second consists of those who escaping from poverty or aloneness *volunteer* to join. Lastly, there are those children used as porters and other forced or risky labors, such as human shields or landmine cleaners.

Due to the international pressure on the Government its Permanent Representative to the UN through a letter to the UNSC in January 2004 stated “*the Myanmar Armed Forces is an all volunteer force and those entering military service do so of their own free will. There is neither a draft system nor forced conscription by the Government of Myanmar. Forced conscription is strictly prohibited.*” (UNSC Press Release)^x

However, organizations monitoring the situation of human rights in Burma continue to denounce a different situation.

“I didn’t want to join. I wanted to go to school, my parents didn’t know where I was... I told them I didn’t want to join. They said: you can’t do anything, you are with us now. I told them I was 12. They said, never mind...” (HRW.2002 Page 26)

Recruitment happens in stations, boat docks, festivals, markets, streets, places near schools, and checkpoints. Children are arrested for minor infractions and abducted; they are taken from the parents by *offering* them education, but they are placed in military schools where they are obliged to join the Army.

Recruiters intimidate boys to *volunteer* by asking their ID cards, and as they fail offer one, they are threatened with a long jail term or told that they can join the army. This abduction method tends to single out children under eighteen for two reasons: it is more probable that children will not know that there is no such a law; and many children under eighteen have not yet obtained such identity cards. The pressure to enlist often is physical, children are grabbed by soldiers and driven to recruit camps, children are kidnapped: “*soldiers forced me into a military vehicle and threatened to shoot me if I tried to escape.*” (Coalition to Stop the Use of Child Soldiers. 2004)^{xi}

Recruiters are paid for the new soldiers they enlist; the price varies according to battalions and regions, but usually it includes cash and 15~20 kilos of rice; soldiers are promoted in exchange for a number of new recruits.

Once recruited, children are taken to *Ye Nyunt* camps: training sites for future soldiers that consist of a network of camps for orphans and other boys separated from their families run by the Army. Tatmadaw enlists boys, keeps them there, at the battalion and provides military training. According to HRW (2002. Page 4), there are 50 to 100 *Ye Nyunt* camps at battalion bases in the country, each with 50 to 200 boys.

5. LIFE AS A BURMESE CHILD SOLDIER

“The youngest was four years old, his name was Ah Ka Bo. He was Karen. He

was there because both of his parents were dead.” (HRW. 2002. Page 40)

“At 12 I was given one bottle of rum a week. The lieutenant provided us cocaine. I put it here, on my thumbnail, which is long, and sniffed it. It was free for us, just before the fight.” (Takkaw. August 2003)^{xiii}

Tatmadaw Child soldiers are at particular risk as they suffer harsh treatment, witness brutal beating, rape and killing, they see civilians killed when they are sick and become *useless* to the Army, these children are pushed to take part in those crimes.

Tatmadaw never notifies parents about the conscription of their kids. Contact with their families is impossible as children are not allowed to write letters or get in touch with the outside world and also due to the permanent re-allocation of villages.

Trainees and soldiers are brutally treated; the slightest mistake results in beatings. They are subject to systematic humiliation and learn to endure harsh and isolated existences, as they cannot cultivate relations that support them.

Leave from the Army is almost never granted until soldiers have served for well over five years. A discharge from the Army is even more difficult to obtain. According to Jagan (2007) *“the biggest obstacle to their release is the need to find replacements for them, any soldier who wants to be discharged must find a substitute.”*

Children do different works, like maintaining the camps, working on moneymaking ventures for the officers. At some training camps the trainees spend as much time doing labor for the officers as they do learning to be soldiers.

Children receive insufficient and poor quality food despite the hard work they are forced to do, and they have their money stolen by officers. *“I was always hungry (...) three members of my class died of tuberculosis in the camp medical clinic (...) it was no good. (...) Sometimes I got my salary; sometimes I didn't because they used my money. I didn't dare complain. We only got rice and yellow beans. Sometimes the commander ordered us to steal vegetables and chickens from the villagers, so we went and stole them.”* (HRW. 2002. Page 75)

During training only some boys go to school, though no one is exempt from military training, which includes marching, -sometimes with their guns on, and being punished if they get tired-, following orders, cleaning, maintaining and using weapons.

Tatmadaw provides little indoctrination; children are to obey unconditionally. Most soldiers do not receive instruction to enhance literacy or occupational skills. This lack of educational opportunities for recruits has significant effects for their post-military futures if they ever manage to leave the army.

Soldiers undergo negative propaganda about rebel groups, they are told that if insurgents capture them, they will be tortured and killed. Instructors tell them that rebels routinely rape, murder and cut the throat of any Burmese soldier taken prisoner. Recruits are told that anyone opposing the Government is a terrorist.

Many participate in direct armed encounters with opposition groups, at times with little or no training, they are provided low quality weapons and they are sent to the front of battalions when attacking in mass.

Children receive only poor quality Chinese medicines while clinics are the last resort. No statistics are available on how many Burmese child soldiers die of preventable and treatable diseases. In many areas where Tatmadaw is deployed, deadly strains of malaria are endemic; children are especially susceptible to such diseases.

In remote regions medical care for soldiers is either sub-standard or non-existent,

mainly to children. *“We never had enough medicine. Children died from insufficient medical treatment, not from injuries, or diseases, that were fatal, rarely soldiers are sent to hospitals, when they are it is too late and most don't return.”* (Hilton)^{xiii}

Children suffer physical and emotional difficulties as a result of the experience of being a soldier. Testimonies talk about experiencing nightmares, anxiety, insomnia, apathy, difficulties in their relations with others, aggressive and withdrawn behaviors, even after years of leaving the army. If they survive, these kids after years of being soldiers are unable to envision a future apart from military service.

6. MAKING THE SOLDIER: MILITARY INSTRUCTION

Children receive the same training as any soldier; if they are not strong enough or if they are too young to go out on operations, they are kept in camps for months or years where they are used as free labor.

Military training includes specialized strategies, like infantry, landmines use, light arms and other secondary exercise such as marching, maintenance of weapons, theory and practical tactics such as deploying troops for battle.

Training with weapons is one of the most dangerous and hard parts of the training for the smallest boys since they cannot manage the weight of weapons and they are at bigger risk due to misuse and mistakes.

Even if they are just teenagers, most of the latest recruits are assigned to ordinary infantry units, where as the newest soldiers they must do the hardest and dirtiest jobs.

Training has a dehumanizing effect. Since the day recruits enter the institution they are pushed to forget their identity and humanity. They are deliberately cut off from their families, brutally treated and prevented from fraternizing. After training, they are separated from those they were recruited with and sent off to distant regions, where they are further brutalized and encouraged to view the local population as enemies.

Young soldiers adapt quickly: *“openly admitting that their first time in battle they were scared, many find that by their second or third time in combat they had lost fear, and some said they almost enjoyed it.”* (HRW. 2002. Page 95)

Though children are drawn into a web of inhumanity and abuses, most never quite lose the sense that something is wrong and learn to rationalize their behavior and take distance from their deeds. When asked about things their units did, they admit that their entire unit committed abuses but they themselves were never part of them.

“I felt nothing against my comrades, they were obeying orders... If I am ordered to kill a baby and I don't, I'll be sentenced to death and someone else would still kill the baby. So I would kill the baby.” (HRW. 2002. Page 96)

“I liked it because we could do anything we liked. When some civilian had something I liked, I just took it without him doing anything. We used to rape women. Anything I wanted to do, I did. I was free.” (Peace Magazine. Page 20)^{xiv}

7. ESCAPING: A DOOR OUT OF HELL?

All children are routinely beaten, yet the situation is worse for those suspected of desertion, they are brutally punished, given long prison terms, forcibly re-recruited, beaten to death or summarily executed. Some times trainees and soldiers are punished *en masse* whenever one of their members runs away. For those who are caught

punishment is so harsh that most boys do not even dare trying.

“Three did it, but one was caught. He had to dive face down on the ground, then every Ye Nyunt boy had to beat him. Some didn’t hit him hard, so the supervisor said I’ll show you and hit him, and then said: Go, hit him like that!” (HRW. 2002.)

“If kids are caught escaping they are beaten with bamboo sticks, put in shackles, poked and then they are taken to the lock-up.” (Teach Kids Peace. 2005)^{xv}

If caught escapees survive they are imprisoned and forced back to the Army. Even if they manage to escape, they can’t return to their homes as they are in camps and areas from where it is nearly impossible to trace their ways back. They are far-off, alone, with no money, no identification and in uniform. Sometimes as they reach the place where their villages used to be they might have been burnt down and resettled.

Despite dangers, desertion is high; soldiers flee from small outposts in remote areas, where they disappear into the forest. For many, the very idea of escaping seems impossible until an opportunity suddenly presents itself, and they take it.

Soldiers flee to neighboring countries, especially to Thailand. The way takes them weeks or months, depending on security; proximity to rebels and to SPDC controlled areas; and distance to the border. They avoid rebel areas since they fear them, they do not speak the language and see the rebels as dangerous enemies, therefore they need to pass unnoticed. Once in the border they are alone, with no one to contact or to ask for help. They try to reach refugee camps thinking they will find safe haven there.

When opposition groups receive these deserters, they scatter them to prevent them from grouping as they are thought of as spies. In trying to be accepted, some join opposition armies and continue fighting though now from the other side.

Burman soldiers that stay illegally in refugee camps are vulnerable to stigmatization by other refugees, they undergo alienation and harassment as they live in camps that are populated, organized and managed by ethnic minorities.

Other than hiding soldiers that escape from Tatmadaw have few options. If they return home to their villages, they risk being arrested and sent to jail followed by conscription back into the army and their families may also be harassed.

Escape means facing dangers like crossing through the jungle alone in conflict zones infected by malaria and dengue; being captured, punished and re-recruited; coming across opposition groups that take them hostage, interrogate and also recruit them.

If they make it to Thailand they live under the threat of deportation to the hands of those from who they escaped due to the application of a *Memorandum of Understanding* on deserting soldiers -an agreement of which everybody talks and fears yet that nobody seems to have real evidence of its existence-.

Refugee camps are not open to deserters and recognition as refugees by host countries is impossible for them to obtain. In such a situation, these children have very limited access to humanitarian assistance. All they can do is survive as they can and live in constant fear of deportation.

The constant abuse, the witnessing of brutal treatment, missing their families and a set of combined reasons eventually push them to take drastic measures. Although most choose to flee, many feel trapped. They fear resistance forces and know that if they flee in Tatmadaw controlled areas they can be easily caught and brutally punished. They know that if they flee, their families will be interrogated and harassed.

SPDC itself has explained that *“according to article 37 of the Defense Services Act,*

any person who deserts or attempts to desert the service shall be court-martialed, and on conviction, be liable to suffer the punishment as handed down by the court-martial."(HRW. 2002. Page 7)

Soldiers know the risk that escaping means; fear simply paralyzes them, alienated in their self-image beyond repair, having lost hope in the future, some of these soldiers choose to kill themselves as the only way out they find.

8. IS DDRR POSSIBLE FOR CHILDREN IN BURMA?

Assisting these children requires a distinction between those in the Tatmadaw and opposition; and those *in* and *outside* Burma, particularly deserters in Thailand. Even if by definition they are all *child soldiers*, they remain different in terms of *why* they are recruited and how to help them.

1) For children in opposition the main strategy is to address the causes that make them *volunteer* and feel they have no other option, namely access to education and jobs. And also addressing the way the Government and the Tatmadaw relate to ethnic minority groups -issue that falls out of the reach of this study-.

As mentioned, some opposition groups have shown interest in demobilizing their children however they lack the resources to provide them opportunities, in this sense the commitment from the international community is essential.

2) In the case of Tatmadaw deserters in Thailand, they hide their past to prevent stigma and to protect themselves from Thai authorities; who deport them in compliance with the *Memorandum of Understanding*.

An important challenge in addressing this group is how to avoid flagging them out and making them more visible. Ethnic salience allows ethnic leaders to locate them and press them to become part of their groups and to go back to the battlefield.

This explains why if they stay in refugee camps, they are treated as *any other refugee* -neglecting their pasts in order to protect them-. Some practitioners argue that in spite of their particular needs, this strategy prevents their stigmatization.

Most organizations working on Burmese issues in Thailand are not openly active in assisting them. This is not to say that help is not offered, but rather that the problem of child soldiers is approached as part of the general *refugee* problem.

For deserters seeking refuge in Thailand, three protection mechanisms were found: one of political nature -advocacy-, another related to actions to assist individuals by *low profile* initiatives -like education and health-, and resettlement in third countries. Yet, only the former constitutes a general strategy, showing little commitment to making real differences for those children's lives. Although *humanitarianly speaking* the issue is relevant, the situation in Thailand is a side effect of the problem in Burma.

3) Given the nature of the conflict in Burma a full-scale DDRR is unlikely to happen in the near future, which irremediably affects these children. However DDRR is a flexible process that does not need to involve every soldier and every side of the conflict. Some DDRR initiatives have had interesting outcomes even if they have only addressed *parts* of armed groups, like children or women. Uganda and in Colombia are examples of how children can be demobilized even in the mist of conflict.

Clearly the best option for child soldiers in Burma is that all four steps -DDRR- take place, nonetheless the process may consist of some of them, for example not all child soldiers need to be disarmed, and reintegration may be impossible. However creative

initiatives have the potential to offer children the chance to stay away from the conflict and to create environments that are more protective than a military setting.

Burma as a sovereign country has the last word on what to do with its army. SPDC committed itself to respect children's rights when in 1991 it acceded the CRC, but so far this promise has not crystallized in real changes.

The Junta signed the *Declaration and Plan of Action* at the World Summit for Children in 1991, and in 1993 it promulgated its Child Law. The same year it approved its *National Program of Action for the Survival, Protection, and Development of Myanmar's Children* and established a *Committee for the Prevention of the Recruitment of Child Soldiers*.

SPDC presented its initial two-year report to the UN Committee on the Rights of the Child with promising advancements in terms of demobilization of children. However not long before that, an NGO called *Images Asia* had released its report *No Childhood At All* that showed a totally different diagnosis to the one presented by the Junta.

In 2002 ILO opened a liaison office in Rangoon; the organization reached an agreement on a *Joint Plan of Action on Forced Labor* with SPDC, which would allow a facilitator to receive complaints from victims of forced labor including child forced recruitment. However, concerns raised in regards to the facilitator's capacity to actually receive any complaint, given the prevailing climate of fear and intimidation.

The government sustains that all procedures aim to prevent and monitor underage conscription during recruitment, training and at entry into active service, however because of mistakes and lack of civil registration some underage were still serving.

Only in 2003 the UN Human Rights Commission adopted Resolution 2003/12 through which it deplored "*the systematic use of child soldiers and other continuing human rights violations in Myanmar.*" The Resolution made a call for immediate action from the government to end the use of forced labor, including those by armed forces. However little had truly happened to bring about actual changes.^{xvi}

Together with UNICEF, SPDC drew a plan to identify and reintegrate child soldiers, developed a birth registration program and established a *Committee for the Prevention of Military Recruitment of Under-Age Children* in January 2004.

Despite official statements, as there is no change in recruitment trends, the only thing the international community has shown to be willing to do is advocacy, as *this is a way to do something without intervening with the internal affairs of the state*^{xvii}. Thus, visible international actions have only aimed at pressing the government as if by saying "*we know what is going on... you should do something to change that*".

Monitoring from UN country team, diplomatic missions, Human Rights organizations and NGOs, continue to denounce thousands of children being mobilized and recruited. For example Jagan (2007) refers to HRW researcher, David Mathieson as stating that "*there may have been a drop in recruitment of children during the Khin Nyunt era, but this has since changed, especially in the last two years with a major renewed offensive against the ethnic minorities in eastern Burma.*"

Recent advancements relate to the UN's Special Representative for Children and Armed Conflict, Radhika Coomaraswamy, visit to Burma that has agreed with the Junta to set up a special post to jointly work on the issue of child soldiers.

The accord set up a *Focal Point* at the Ministry of Social Welfare; as a monitoring mechanism with the assistance of UN agencies in Burma, especially UNICEF. The

team should be in charge of gathering information on the extent of the problem, implementing some DDDR and reporting it to the UN Security Council later this year.

In so doing the discredited Junta has committed itself *again* to cut the recruitment of children. Let us remember that human rights groups and UN reports have criticized Burma for its widespread recruiting of child soldiers over the past two decades.

In spite of how promising these advancements seem in terms of reducing child recruitment, Jagan (2007) points at two key issues: 1) the release of soldiers that were abducted before they were 18, but have reached adulthood -who, by definition are child soldiers-. And 2) the fact that there might be as many as 90,000 child soldiers, whose discharge is almost impossible due to the replacement principle to which we referred before in page 4.

Clearly, UN officials have *overlooked* these issues, maybe to avoid too much pressure that may cause the Junta to, once again, dump its promises to stop recruitment of minors. UN officials show optimism, yet observers remain skeptical, especially after the President of the International Committee for the Red Cross openly accused the Junta in June of this year of committing violations of international humanitarian law by abusing civilians and causing immense suffering.^{xviii} Adding to the effort of believing what the Junta states, it is already clear that any progress will be hard to screen as UN officials have admitted “*it will be difficult to monitor the activities of local recruiters throughout the country, especially in remoter areas.*” (Jagan. 2007)

Evidently the international community has only been able (willing?) of flagging out recruiters -*name and shame*- but no concrete measures have yet taken place. Within this framework, little is being done -and only for individual cases at the time of responding to children’s needs-. Until general demobilization of children takes place rehabilitation and reintegration are processes that cannot logically happen.

Except for specific exceptions all the organizations that were interviewed for the present study told they have no particular programs to assist Burmese child soldiers.

So far the international community has *recommended* SPDC to recognize special protection for its children. Yet, it seems that the existence of systematic violence against them, particularly military recruitment was not in itself a source of legitimacy for the actions that should be taken in the name of the *Responsibility to Protect*.

Child military conscription violates the international law, Burma’s national laws and the government’s and opposition groups’ commitments. The fact that Burma is the world’s leading user of child soldiers makes it a unique case, a case where immediate action to end recruitment of children, demobilize and reintegrate them is a must.

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ⁱ CSW Report. *Child Soldiers And Gang-Rape Survivors In Burma Give Testimonies*

ⁱⁱ Becker, J. *Burma: World's Highest Number of Child Soldiers*

ⁱⁱⁱ Human Rights Watch. *Burma Demobilize Child Soldiers*

^{iv} UNICEF. *Adults wars, Child Soldiers*

^v Irrawaddy, Yeni. *UN accuses Burma of still recruiting child soldiers*

^{vi} From interviews carried out for this study

^{vii} From interviews carried out for this study

^{viii} Singer Peter W. describes the use of children as soldiers in contemporary warfare as a *doctrine*, a new policy in the rules of war, the author provides a definition by saying “*doctrines are what militaries think of as a set of guidelines about the use of force*”. Page 6.

^{ix} Jagan, Larry. Bangkok Post. July 10, 2007. *UN envoy upbeat over child soldiers in Burma. Her optimism, however, runs counter to other international organisations' assessment.*

^x UN Security Council Press Release SC/7985.

^{xi} Coalition to Stop the Use of Child Soldiers. *Child soldiers use 2003: A Briefing for the 4th UN*

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